

Growth of Large Ti_3AlC_2 Single Crystals via TiAl_3 Flux: Properties and Toward Millimetre-Scale MXenes

Bing Wu^{1,*}, Fedor Lipilin¹, Xiaodong Liu², Jan Luxa¹, RuiZhi Yu³, Martin Vesely⁴, Kalyan Jyoti Sarkar¹, Filipa M. Oliveira¹, Lei Zheng¹, Yulong Ying⁵, B. Layla Mehdi², Zdenek Sofer^{1,*}

¹ Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic, E-mail: wui@vscht.cz and zdenek.sofer@vscht.cz

² Department of Materials, Design & Manufacturing Engineering, University of Liverpool, Liverpool L69 3GH, UK

³ Institute of Micro/Nano Materials and Devices, Ningbo University of Technology, Ningbo, Zhejiang 315211, P.R. China

⁴ Department of Organic Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic

⁵ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Zhejiang Sci-Tech University, Hangzhou, 310018, P. R. China

ABSTRACT

Ti_3AlC_2 , a typical MAX phase compound, serves as the parent structure of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes, the most extensively studied member of the MXene family for diverse applications. Despite the growing interest, most experimental studies on Ti_3AlC_2 rely on polycrystalline samples, limiting the accurate determination of its intrinsic physical properties. The synthesis of large, high-quality single crystals remains a significant challenge, yet it is essential for probing fundamental electronic, optical, and transport behaviours. In this work, we report the first successful growth of high-quality centimetre-scale Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals via a TiAl_3 flux-based approach. The crystals exhibit excellent structural quality, with individual flakes exceeding 1 cm in length and basal-plane surface areas reaching up to $\sim 36 \text{ mm}^2$. Hall measurements on individual flakes reveal a high carrier density of $\sim 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, while polarisation-resolved Raman spectra show a nearly circular intensity pattern, indicating optical isotropy within the basal plane. To investigate surface characteristics, scanning tunnelling microscopy was performed on freshly cleaved crystals, revealing non-flat surface topography influenced by cleavage termination. First-principles calculations indicate that cleavage predominantly occurs between Ti–Al layers and reveal distinct surface-dependent band structures and Fermi surfaces. A nearly regular hexagonal Fermi contour corresponds to the Al-terminated surface, while a star-like sixfold modulated contour is associated with the Ti-terminated surface. Chemical etching of these MAX phase crystals yields millimetre-scale $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ flakes, which can be mechanically exfoliated onto chips. Raman spectra exhibit a strong G-band peak at $\sim 1550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, with no discernible D-band, indicating low-defect sp^2 -like carbon structures. Two-terminal devices fabricated from these flakes display symmetric I–V characteristics and negligible gate modulation across $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ channels, confirming metallic behaviour and good electrical contact. This work establishes a scalable route to large Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals, offering new insights into their intrinsic properties, laying a solid foundation for future MXene-based device technologies.

KEYWORDS: Single crystal, Ti_3AlC_2 , MAX phase, DFT, Fermi surface, MXene

INTRODUCTION

Two-dimensional (2D) transition metal carbides and nitrides, commonly known as MXenes, have attracted considerable attention in recent years owing to their tunable surface chemistry, high metallic conductivity, and exceptional performance in energy storage, catalysis, and electromagnetic shielding.¹⁻³ Among the various members of the MXene family, $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ stands out as the most extensively studied representative, owing to its relatively simple synthesis and broad range of functional properties.⁴ This material is typically obtained by selectively etching the “A” element, most commonly aluminum, from a layered ternary carbide known as Ti_3AlC_2 . The parent compound Ti_3AlC_2 belongs to the $\text{M}_{n+1}\text{AX}_n$ family of MAX phases (where $n = 1, 2, 3,$ or 4), which are characterized by a hexagonal structure composed of alternating layers of a transition metal (M), an A-group element (A, typically from group IIIA or IVA), and carbon and/or nitrogen (X).^{5, 6} Within this family, Ti_3AlC_2 represents the prototypical 312-phase and serves as a primary precursor for generating high-quality $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene through chemical exfoliation. While significant efforts have been directed toward optimizing the properties of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ through surface termination control and post-synthetic treatments, a fundamental understanding of its precursor Ti_3AlC_2 remains relatively limited.

Previous studies on Ti_3AlC_2 have predominantly employed polycrystalline powders or sintered ceramics, which are inherently limited by their structural disorder, small grain size, and lack of well-defined surfaces.⁷ These features render them unsuitable for probing intrinsic anisotropic properties or surface-sensitive phenomena, such as those accessible via polarized Raman spectroscopy, scanning tunneling microscopy (STM), or angle-resolved photoemission spectroscopy (ARPES). In particular, the presence of grain boundaries and chemical inhomogeneities often obscures transport measurements and prevents reliable comparisons with theoretical predictions.^{8, 9} To address these issues, recent efforts have explored the growth of Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals. For instance, Zhang et al. synthesized millimeter-scale crystals using a horizontal temperature gradient approach, achieving lateral sizes of up to $\sim 9 \text{ mm}^2$.¹⁰ However, this method requires careful thermal field design and complex flux control, resulting in limited scalability. Moreover, the as-grown crystals display morphological inhomogeneity and evidence of overlapping domains, as indicated by their stepped surfaces and X-ray diffraction patterns, which suggests the presence of residual grain boundaries. These issues, combined with the low yield, restrict their utility for surface-sensitive studies or device-level applications, where large, uniform, and defect-free single crystals are essential. Moreover, these small sizes significantly hinder mechanical exfoliation and direct transfer processes essential for physical device fabrication. Earlier efforts based on self-flux or chemical vapor transport methods yielded even smaller crystals ($< 80 \mu\text{m}$), often with multi-domain structures or rough surface morphologies.¹¹ While the synthesis of other MAX-phase or related single crystals, such as V-based MAX, MAB series, or Cr_2AlC , has been reported, these efforts remain material-specific and often lack generalizability to Ti-Al-C systems.¹²⁻¹⁵

Notably, very few studies have addressed the critical impact of surface termination, namely Ti-terminated versus Al-terminated facets, on the electronic structure, surface band dispersion, or Fermi surface morphology of Ti_3AlC_2 . This knowledge gap is particularly

relevant for understanding MXene exfoliation mechanisms and surface reactivity, as cleavage behavior directly determines termination-dependent properties in the resulting $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ flakes.

As a result, the synthesis of large, high-quality Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals remains a significant challenge in the field. This limitation not only prevents direct access to intrinsic transport, optical, and surface electronic properties, but also severely constrains our ability to understand cleavage energetics, surface reconstructions, and termination-selective band structures, factors that ultimately rule MXene production quality and interface engineering. In particular, the effect of the cleavage interface on defect density, flake integrity, and terminal group distribution in derived $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene remains poorly understood. Despite the pivotal role of these aspects, systematic investigations using pristine, macroscale single-crystal MAX phases are still absent from the current results.

In this work, we report a step forward in the growth of large-area, high-purity Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals using a TiAl_3 -assisted flux growth strategy. By leveraging the high Al activity of the TiAl_3 binary eutectic, we overcome the limitations associated with conventional melt or self-flux methods. At low TiAl_3 flux concentrations, high-purity Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals with lateral sizes of $\sim 50\ \mu\text{m}$ can already be obtained. Increasing the flux content further enables the growth of centimeter-scale crystals with well-developed basal planes, suitable for mechanical cleaving and device integration. Structural and transport measurements reveal a high crystalline quality and metallic conductivity, while polarization-resolved Raman spectroscopy demonstrates nearly perfect in-plane optical isotropy. STM studies on cleaved surfaces uncover termination-dependent topography and terrace formation, and first-principles calculations reveal distinct surface electronic structures, with regular hexagonal Fermi contours for the Al-terminated surface and sixfold star-like contours for the Ti-terminated surface.

Finally, we demonstrate that high-quality $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene flakes can be derived from these single crystals via conventional chemical etching and mechanical exfoliation. The resulting MXene exhibits negligible D-band intensity in Raman spectra and symmetric I–V characteristics in two-terminal devices, indicating low defect density and excellent electronic quality. Overall, this work not only establishes a scalable route toward high-quality Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals but also opens new opportunities to investigate termination-specific surface physics and to fabricate high-quality MXenes for electronic devices from structurally well-defined precursors.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals. Elemental powders of Ti (ThermoScientific, Germany, >99.5% pure, 300 mesh), Al (ThermoScientific, Germany, >99.5% pure, 300 mesh), TiC (ThermoScientific, Germany, >99.5% pure, 300 mesh), hydrochloric acid (Penta, Czech Republic, 37wt%).

Synthesis of MAX phase. Stoichiometric amounts of TiC, Ti, and Al powders were thoroughly ground using a mortar and pestle for 15 minutes. The mixture was then transferred to an alumina crucible and compacted. The crucible was placed in an alumina tube furnace under a continuous argon flow (10 sccm). The furnace temperature was ramped to 750 °C at a rate of 5 °C/min and held for 2 hours, followed by a ramp to 1500 °C at 10 °C/min and held for 4 hours. The system was then cooled to room temperature at a rate of 10 °C/min under the

same argon flow.

Synthesis of MXene. Large-sized MXene sheets were obtained from single-crystal MAX by etching several bulk MAX pieces in 50 mL of 5% HF solution. The reaction was conducted under static, argon-filled conditions without stirring for two weeks, followed by repeated washing with deionised water.

X-ray Diffraction (XRD). Phase analysis was performed using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer (Germany) equipped with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). The measurements were carried out at 40 kV and 40 mA with a step size of 0.02° .

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM). SEM and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analyses were conducted using a Tescan MAIA 3 system, integrated with an Oxford EDS detector and operated via Aztec software (TESCAN Brno, s.r.o., Brno, Czech Republic).

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). Lamellae were extracted using a FEI Helios 5 Laser plasma focused ion beam (p-FIB) system equipped with an Xe⁺ ion column, an electron column, a multi-channel gas injector system, and an EasyLift micromanipulator. High-resolution TEM (HR-TEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) were conducted on a Cs-corrected JEOL 2100F-Cs TEM/STEM operated at 200 kV.

Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD). EBSD analysis was performed using a Tescan Lyra3 GMU dual-beam scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with EDS, EBSD, STEM, and TOF-SIMS detectors (TESCAN Brno, s.r.o., Brno, Czech Republic).

Raman Spectroscopy. Raman measurements were performed in an argon-filled glovebox using a WITec alpha300R confocal Raman microscope equipped with a 532 nm laser (WITec GmbH, Ulm, Germany). The microscope was mounted on an anti-vibration table to minimise external disturbances. Spectra were collected at ambient temperature using a Zeiss EC Epiplan-Neofluar DIC 100 \times /0.9 objective lens, a 600 g/mm grating (blaze wavelength: 500 nm), and a laser power of 5 mW.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). The surface composition of the samples was analysed using a SPECS XPS system equipped with a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.7 \text{ eV}$) and a hemispherical electron energy analyser (Phoibos 150, SPECS GmbH, Berlin, Germany).

Hall Measurements. Hall effect measurements were conducted on bulk Ti₃AlC₂ using a DX-100 Hall measurement system (Chinese Academy of Sciences, China). Four symmetric contacts were made at the corners of the Ti₃AlC₂ flake using silver paste. The sample thickness was measured to be 80 μm . Measurements were performed at 300 K with an applied current of 1 mA and a magnetic field sweep range from 100 to 500 mT.

Scanning Tunnelling Microscopy (STM). STM measurements were performed using a Nanosurf CoreAFM system equipped with a platinum (Pt) probe (Nanosurf AG, Liestal, Switzerland).

Electrical measurements. Thin MXene flakes were mechanically exfoliated from bulk crystals using the scotch tape method and subsequently transferred onto chips via PDMS stamping for electrical characterisation (as schematically presented in **Figure S10a**). Electrical measurements were performed using a Keysight source/measure unit (B2902A)

and an Instec HCP421V-MPS Vacuum Chamber Probe Station placed on a Speirs Robertson antivibration unit at ambient conditions.

Calculations. All density functional theory (DFT) calculations were carried out using the projector augmented wave (PAW) method as implemented in the GPAW code, interfaced via the Atomic Simulation Environment (ASE).^{16, 17} The exchange-correlation interactions were treated using the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) functional within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA).¹⁸ A plane-wave basis set with a kinetic energy cutoff of 500 eV was employed for all structure optimisations. The Brillouin zone was sampled using a Monkhorst–Pack grid of $18 \times 18 \times 6$ for bulk Ti_3AlC_2 to ensure convergence and to obtain a smooth Fermi surface. The calculated Fermi surface was visualised and analysed using the XCrySDen package. For slab models with large supercells, only the Γ -point was used to sample the Brillouin zone due to the increased computational cost. To account for long-range van der Waals interactions, DFT-D3 dispersion corrections were included throughout the calculations.¹⁹ Geometry optimisations were performed using the BFGS algorithm until the maximum force on the movable atom in each image was below $0.03 \text{ eV}/\text{\AA}$ per iteration. The bulk MXene model was constructed based on a composition of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2(\text{O}_{0.1}\text{F}_{1.1}(\text{OH})_{1.8})$, and the corresponding Brillouin zone was sampled using a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ k-point mesh.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An initial attempt to synthesise Ti_3AlC_2 under high Al flux conditions revealed critical limitations in phase selectivity. As shown in **Figure S1**, when Al was added in excess relative to the standard Ti_3AlC_2 stoichiometry, the resulting XRD patterns exhibited a clear compositional shift. At $1.2 \times$ Al (**Figure S1a**), Ti_3AlC_2 remained the dominant phase, accompanied by a minor amount of Ti_2Al_5 . Upon increasing the Al content to $2.0 \times$ (**Figure S1b**), Ti_3AlC_2 was still present but accompanied by trace TiC and TiAl_3 phases. However, at $10 \times$ excess Al (**Figure S1c**), the Ti_3AlC_2 phase completely disappeared, and the products consisted solely of TiC and TiAl_3 , indicating a strong suppression of MAX phase formation under high Al flux conditions. Inspired by these findings, a new synthesis strategy was developed in which TiAl_3 was intentionally used as a soluble flux, and the stoichiometry was compensated by adding TiC, Ti, and Al in a molar ratio of 2: 1: 1 to match the target Ti_3AlC_2 phase (**Figure S2a**). The resulting product synthesised under a Ti_3AlC_2 : TiAl_3 molar ratio of 1: 1, exhibited the desired phase purity and a quasi-hexagonal platelet morphology, consistent with the hexagonal crystal symmetry (space group $P6_3/mmc$) of Ti_3AlC_2 . SEM imaging, EDS mapping, and XRD analysis confirmed the homogeneous elemental distribution and structural integrity of the synthesised MAX phase (**Figure S2b–d**).

To further improve the crystallinity and size of the Ti_3AlC_2 crystals, the flux ratio was increased to Ti_3AlC_2 : TiAl_3 = 1: 50. As shown in **Figure 1**, the resulting crystals exhibit a well-defined plate-like morphology with lateral dimensions up to centimetres and surface areas reaching $\sim 36 \text{ mm}^2$ (**Figure 1b**). Additionally, as shown in **Figure S3**, the large flux environment enables dispersed growth of crystals throughout the flux matrix, consistent with a dissolution–reprecipitation growth mechanism. XRD patterns recorded from individual flakes display only the (001) reflections—002, 004, 006, 008, 0014, and 0016—demonstrating the formation of highly oriented single crystals along the c-axis (**Figure 1a**). SEM imaging reveals smooth, layered surfaces (**Figure 1c**), while EDS analysis confirms a Ti : Al : C atomic ratio close to 3 : 0.9 : 2 (**Figure 1d**), consistent with the target composition.

Further structural verification was provided by high-resolution TEM. The crystal structure of Ti_3AlC_2 , viewed along the c-axis, is shown in **Figure 1e**, illustrating the characteristic layered arrangement of Ti, Al, and C atoms within the hexagonal crystal symmetry. High-resolution TEM imaging further confirms the well-ordered, layered morphology of the crystals (**Figure 1f**). SAED pattern taken along the [001] zone axis (**Figure 1g**) matches well with the corresponding simulated diffraction pattern (**Figure 1h**), collectively verifying the high crystallinity and structural fidelity of the synthesised MAX phase. EBSD mapping in **Figure S4** was performed to assess the crystallographic orientation of the synthesised Ti_3AlC_2 crystals. As the Ti_3AlC_2 phase is not included in the standard SEM EBSD database, a structurally analogous phase, Ti_3Al (hexagonal, space group $P6_3/mmc$), was selected as a reference due to its identical crystal symmetry. The EBSD orientation map shows uniform contrast and colour across the entire scanned area, with no detectable grain boundaries, indicating that all regions share the same crystallographic orientation. This provides strong evidence that the sample is a single crystal.

Figure 1 Structural and morphological characterisation of Ti_3AlC_2 crystals synthesised using TiC, Ti, and Al with a molar ratio of 2: 1: 1 to achieve stoichiometric balance for Ti_3AlC_2 , and TiAl_3 as a flux with a Ti_3AlC_2 : TiAl_3 molar ratio of 1: 50. (a) XRD pattern of the Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals. (b) Photograph of the as-grown crystals. (c) SEM image and (d) corresponding EDS spectrum. (e) Crystal structure of Ti_3AlC_2 viewed along the c-axis. (f) Cross-sectional HRTEM image showing the layered morphology. (g) SAED pattern taken along the [001] zone axis and (h) corresponding simulated diffraction pattern.

Ti_3AlC_2 is composed of layers of Ti-C octahedra interleaved with Al atomic planes stacked along the crystallographic c-axis. To investigate the interlayer interactions and intrinsic

properties of this layered MAX phase, cleaved Ti_3AlC_2 flakes were exfoliated onto Si/SiO_2 substrates using a standard mechanical exfoliation method. The preparation of clean, exfoliated crystals facilitated direct spectroscopic and electronic characterisation. A schematic depiction of the Raman-active vibrational modes (**Figure 2b**) reveals the atomic motions contributing to these characteristic peaks, involving collective vibrations of Ti, Al, and C atoms within the layered structure.²⁰ These vibrational features are directly related to the bonding environment and structural stability of Ti_3AlC_2 . Raman spectroscopy performed on freshly cleaved crystals (**Figure 2a**) exhibited distinct vibrational modes characteristic of the Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phase, specifically observed at $\omega_1 = 126.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\omega_2 = 183.7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\omega_3 = 200.7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\omega_4 = 272.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\omega_5 = 632.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\omega_6 = 650.9 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are consistent with reported results in experiment and calculation.²⁰ Polarisation-dependent Raman analysis from 0 to 360° (**Figure 2c-d**) further demonstrated the basal-plane isotropy of the optical response. Specifically, the nearly circular intensity distribution for both the A_{1g} (ω_4) and E_{2g} (ω_3) modes indicates minimal structural anisotropy within the basal plane, consistent with the hexagonal symmetry of the crystal lattice.²¹

High-resolution XPS spectra (**Figure 2e**) further provided the surface composition of the MAX structure. The deconvoluted core-level spectra for Ti 2p, Al 2p, and C 1s were well-defined as summarised in **Table S1**. Specifically, the Ti 2p core level exhibited a spin-orbit doublet with the Ti 2p_{3/2} peak at 454.3 eV (FWHM: 0.94 eV) and the Ti 2p_{1/2} peak at 460.3 eV (FWHM: 1.41 eV), yielding a spin-orbit splitting ΔBE of 6.0 eV, consistent with Ti in the MAX phase.^{22, 23} Similarly, the Al 2p core level showed a doublet with the Al 2p_{3/2} peak at 71.6 eV (FWHM: 0.62 eV) and the Al 2p_{1/2} peak at 72.1 eV (FWHM: 0.62 eV), with a ΔBE of 0.5 eV, indicative of pure, non-oxidized aluminum within the structure. For the C 1s spectrum, a prominent peak at 281.9 eV (FWHM: 0.50 eV) was observed, definitively assigned to the Ti-C bond characteristic of the MAX phase, while a peak at 285 eV (FWHM: 1.89 eV) was attributed to adventitious carbon (C-C/C-O). The sharp, well-resolved peaks and the absence of shifted contributions from oxidized states confirm the high structural uniformity and chemical purity of the crystals, which are critical for reliable interpretation of electronic structure and transport properties.

The transport properties of the Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phase were investigated through Hall measurements (**Figure S5**), revealing the interplay between bulk carrier concentration, mobility, and conductivity as a function of magnetic field. The bulk carrier concentration, initially around 10^{20} cm^{-3} at 100 mT, exhibited a sharp increase, peaking at $5 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ at 400 mT. The carrier mobility displayed a significant decrease from an initial high of approximately $23 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$ at 100 mT to lower values below $5 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$ in the higher magnetic field range (200-500 mT). This reduction in mobility with increasing magnetic field is primarily attributed to the magnetoresistance effect, where the Lorentz force causes charge carrier trajectories to curve, diminishing their effective forward velocity.²⁴ Despite this varying mobility, the overall conductivity generally showed a robust increasing trend with the magnetic field, starting from approximately $388 (\Omega\cdot\text{cm})^{-1}$ at 100 mT and reaching about $403 (\Omega\cdot\text{cm})^{-1}$ at 500 mT. This high carrier concentration, coupled with substantial conductivity, further supports the observed metallic character typical of MAX phases.²⁵

Figure 2 (a) Raman spectrum of a cleaved Ti_3AlC_2 crystal. (b) Schematic illustration of the Raman-active vibrational modes in Ti_3AlC_2 . (c) Polarised Raman intensity of the A_{1g} mode (ω_4) and (d) E_{2g} mode (ω_3) as a function of polarisation angle ($0^\circ - 360^\circ$). (e) High-resolution XPS spectra of Ti 2p, Al 2p, and C 1s core levels.

The morphology of the cleaved surfaces is further investigated using high-resolution STM. As shown in **Figure 3a**, the cleaved Ti_3AlC_2 surface exhibits an inhomogeneous topographic contrast in the STM image, with regions of variable brightness and irregular texture. Such features indicate a non-uniform cleavage behavior, likely arising from mixed surface terminations and atomic-scale roughness at the exposed interface. Unlike the ideal layered step morphology observed in some van der Waals materials, the presence of chemically distinct Ti, C, and Al layers in Ti_3AlC_2 leads to preferential but imperfect cleavage. This can result in coexisting domains terminated by either Ti, C or Al, consistent with the observed contrast fluctuations. These observations suggest that the cleaved surface is structurally and chemically heterogeneous, which may influence subsequent MXene etching behavior. To better understand the possible cleavage planes, we constructed structural models depicting three representative cleavage scenarios: between Ti and Al layers (Ti-Al), between the outer Ti layer and C (Ti'-C'), and between the inner Ti layer and C (Ti''-C''), as illustrated in **Figure 3b**. The corresponding exfoliation energies ($\Delta E = E_{\text{bulk}} - [E_{\text{exfoliated}} + E_{\text{remaining}}]$) were calculated and are presented in **Figure 3c**. Among the three configurations, cleavage at the Ti-Al interface shows the lowest exfoliation energy (-7.8 eV), in contrast to the much higher energies for breaking Ti-C' (-26.2 eV) or Ti-C'' (-18.9 eV) bonds. This energetic preference suggests that mechanical or chemical exfoliation is likely

to produce surfaces terminated either by Ti or by Al, depending on the precise cleavage termination.

To clarify the effect of surface termination on the electronic structure, five surface models with varying degrees of Al coverage, from fully Al-terminated (Al4) to fully Al-depleted (Al0), were examined, as illustrated in **Figure 3d**. The projected density of states (PDOS) shows that Al *p* orbitals contribute primarily to energies below the Fermi level, with their intensity decreasing smoothly as energy approaches the Fermi level. In contrast, Ti *d* and Ti *p* orbitals dominate the states around the Fermi level across all configurations, confirming their central role in surface electronic behavior. Notably, Ti *p* orbital contributions increase progressively from Al4 to Al0, indicating an enhancement of Ti–Ti orbital overlap or surface state formation as Al is removed. These results reveal that Ti orbitals primarily govern surface electronic characteristics, while Al serves a secondary role confined to deeper valence states. The corresponding band structures of these five surface terminations, along with the bulk Ti_3AlC_2 , are shown in **Figure S6**. All configurations maintain metallic character, but noticeable differences appear near the Fermi level depending on the surface composition. A progressive upward shift in the Fermi level is also observed from Al4 to Al0. This trend arises from the gradual replacement of Al atoms by Ti at the surface, resulting in increased surface electron density and enhanced contributions from Ti *d* and *p* orbitals near the Fermi energy. The electronic structure thus becomes increasingly surface-dominated and metallic as the termination evolves toward Ti-rich configurations.

Figure 3e compares the termination-dependent Fermi surface contours at various energy slices ($E_f \pm 0.2, \pm 0.4$ eV). The Ti-terminated surface, with a higher Fermi level and stronger Ti *d*-orbital contributions, mimics a hole-doped character relative to Al-terminated ones. Its Fermi contour exhibits a sixfold, star-like modulation at E_f , which becomes increasingly warped and petal-shaped under hole doping ($E_f - 0.4$ eV), indicating enhanced surface-state localisation and anisotropy. In contrast, the Al-terminated surface shows a symmetric hexagonal contour that evolves into a nearly circular pocket upon electron doping ($E_f + 0.4$ eV), suggesting the filling of more delocalized, conduction-like states. These results highlight the distinct electronic environments induced by surface terminations, with direct implications for charge transport, work function tuning, and MXene exfoliation behaviour.

Figure 3 (a) STM image of a freshly cleaved Ti_3AlC_2 surface showing atomically flat terraces and step edges, indicative of layered cleavage behavior. (b) Schematic illustration of possible cleavage planes within the Ti_3AlC_2 lattice. (c) DFT-calculated cleavage energies for different crystallographic planes, showing a clear energetic preference for separation between Ti and Al layers. (d) Surface models with varying Al terminations (Al4 to Al0) and their corresponding total and projected density of states (DOS). Ti-rich terminations exhibit higher Fermi levels and stronger Ti *d*-orbital contributions near E_f . (e) Termination-dependent Fermi surface contours at $E_f \pm 0.2$ and ± 0.4 eV.

Following the successful synthesis of large, high-quality Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phase single crystals using the TiAl_3 flux-based approach, we next subjected the single crystals to selective A-layer removal via HF etching (please see Experimental section for details) to obtain $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene and assess the quality and structural integrity of the resulting 2D flakes. **Figure 4** presents the morphology and chemical composition of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ flakes obtained via chemical etching of the as-grown Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals. As shown in **Figure 4a**, isolated MXene flakes with lateral sizes exceeding 1 mm^2 were obtained, demonstrating the potential of these large-area single crystals for mechanical exfoliation. In fact, even larger MXene flakes are possible; however, partial fragmentation occurred during cleaning and transfer steps after etching. Elemental mapping (**Figure 4b**) reveals uniform distributions of Ti and F across

the entire flake. To quantify the etching efficiency and surface composition, EDS analyses were performed on both the mapped region (**Figure S7a**) and a carbon-tape-free area (**Figure S7b**). In both cases, the Al signal is below the detection limit, confirming effective A-layer removal. The atomic ratios in **Figure S7b** approximate Ti: C: F = 3: 2: 1.1, consistent with the stoichiometry of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2(-\text{F}_{1.1}(-\text{O}/\text{OH})_{0.9})$, validating the formation of high-purity MXene with low-defect termination chemistry. **Figure 4c** further confirms the well-ordered lamellar architecture and high degree of exfoliation.

To verify the phase identity and structural ordering of the as-prepared MXene, XRD was performed on a single flake. As shown in **Figure 4d**, the diffraction pattern exhibits a series of (00l) reflections, characteristic of a well-aligned $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ layered structure. The sharp (002) peak located at $2\theta = 9.1^\circ$ indicates a large interlayer spacing, associated with the intercalation of surface terminations ($-\text{O}$, $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{F}$). The higher-order peaks ((004), (006), (008), and (0010)) further confirm the excellent c-axis orientation and long-range lamellar periodicity of the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene. The inset photograph highlights the freestanding MXene flake, exhibiting a dark-purple color. DFT simulations were performed on both bulk and monolayer $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ models with mixed $-\text{F}$, $-\text{OH}$, and $-\text{O}$ terminations ($\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{F}_{1.1}\text{O}_{0.1}(\text{OH})_{0.8}$). As shown in **Figure S8a–c**, the simulated XRD pattern of the bulk structure closely matches the experimental one in **Figure 4d**, reproducing the (002) reflection at $\sim 9.1^\circ$ and higher-order peaks, thus confirming the accuracy of the termination composition. Additionally, the DOS shown in **Figure S8d** reveals a metallic nature dominated by Ti *d* orbitals near the Fermi level. In contrast to the well-ordered Fermi surfaces observed in pristine Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phases (**Figure 3e**), the calculated Fermi surface of multilayer $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene (**Figure S9**) reveals a highly irregular and fragmented topology. The loss of crystallographic symmetry and the emergence of numerous narrow, warped contours reflect the disorder introduced by surface terminations and interlayer interactions. Such complex features suggest substantial anisotropy and scattering in charge transport, which may affect the electronic mobility and interface behaviour in device applications.

To further investigate the structural integrity and surface terminations of the synthesized MXene flakes, Raman spectroscopy was performed. **Figure 4e** presents the Raman spectrum of the exfoliated $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene flakes. Multiple characteristic peaks are observed in the low-frequency region ($127\text{--}715\text{ cm}^{-1}$), corresponding to Ti–C vibrations and surface terminations, in agreement with previous reports on Raman spectroscopy of MXenes.^{4, 26, 27} The peak at 715 cm^{-1} is attributed to the $\text{A}_{1g}(\text{C})$ vibrational mode, which is characteristic of multilayer $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene, in line with the layered architecture observed in **Figure 4c**.²⁷ A pronounced peak near 1557 cm^{-1} is identified as a G-band-like mode, typically attributed to surface graphitic domains or conjugated C=C species. Notably, the D-band is barely visible, indicating a low level of disordered sp^2 carbon. The broad shoulder at $\sim 1248\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may arise from oxidation-related scattering or vibrational contributions of terminal groups. These spectral features collectively suggest partial surface restructuring without severe degradation of the carbon backbone after the etching.

Figure 4 Characterisation of etched $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ flakes. (a) SEM image of a freestanding MXene flake with lateral dimensions >1 mm. (b) Elemental mapping of Ti, C, F, and O. (c) Cross-sectional SEM image revealing the layered architecture of the exfoliated flake. (d) XRD pattern of a $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ flake. (e) Raman spectrum of an exfoliated $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene flake and inset of the corresponding photograph of MXene transferred on chips for Raman.

To evaluate the electrical transport properties of individual delaminated $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ flakes, we performed mechanical exfoliation followed by transfer onto chips with SiO_2/Si substrates, as illustrated in **Figure 5a**. Two-terminal devices with patterned Au contacts were then fabricated, as shown in **Figure 5b** and **Figure S10**. A representative SEM image of a flake bridging the electrode gap is provided in **Figure S11**. Due to the transfer process, the MXene surface in contact with the substrate exhibits noticeable wrinkles. AFM measurements (**Figure S11c** and **d**) on relatively flat regions yield an average thickness of ~ 28 nm. The I–V characteristics in **Figure 4c** exhibit a symmetric, slightly nonlinear response with negligible hysteresis between forward and reverse scans, suggesting the formation of continuous conductive junctions with low contact resistance. **Figure 4d** shows the gate-dependent response under ± 10 V back-gating, where the drain current remains nearly constant, indicating metallic behaviour or a degenerate semiconductor state with high carrier density. These results confirm the high electrical conductivity of exfoliated $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ flakes and their compatibility with microfabricated devices. Importantly, the ability to obtain $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ flakes with lateral sizes exceeding 1 mm^2 from a single-crystal Ti_3AlC_2 represents a significant step forward in the MXene synthesis, as conventional top-down methods of MXenes typically yield much smaller and more defective flakes. Even in comparison to bottom-up techniques such as chemical vapour deposition (CVD), which have produced Mo_2C crystals with lateral

sizes ranging from 10 to 100 μm , or more recently, the growth of Ti_2CCl_2 sheets, our approach achieves significantly larger flake areas, underscoring its scalability, accessibility, and industrial relevance.²⁸⁻³⁰

Figure 5 (a) Schematic of mechanical exfoliation and transfer of MXenes to chips. (b) Schematic of a two-terminal MXene device with $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ flakes bridging Au electrodes on SiO_2/Si substrate. (c) Output characteristics showing symmetric and hysteresis-free I - V curves. (d) Transfer characteristics (I_{DS} vs. U_{G}).

The use of TiAl_3 flux enables the growth of large, high-purity Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals with atomically flat surfaces, serving as an ideal platform for producing structurally uniform MXene flakes. This top-down route eliminates the need for complex setups typical of CVD, while offering precise control over crystal morphology and surface termination. With centimetre-scale MAX phase crystals as starting materials, this work will also potentially allow the use of different etching methods, termination-specific surface engineering, and the synthesis of other MXene compositions using well-defined single-crystal precursors.

Such control is essential given the multifunctional properties of MXenes, including excellent electrical conductivity, tunable work function, abundant free-charge carriers, and compatibility with methods compatible with the micro- and nanofabrication of MXene devices, including spin coating, spray coating, and dip coating methods.³¹ Since these properties are highly sensitive to both the transition metal chemistry and surface termination, the ability to precisely control synthesis conditions is essential. By addressing these parameters, our approach provides a pathway toward integrating large-area MXene flakes into electronic-compatible platforms, enabling their use in memory devices, contact electrodes for photodetectors, sensors, among other next-generation devices.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this work establishes a robust framework for understanding and engineering the structural and electronic characteristics of Ti_3AlC_2 and its derived MXenes from the perspective of bulk crystallography and surface physics. By leveraging TiAl_3 flux chemistry, we successfully synthesised centimetre-scale Ti_3AlC_2 crystals with high structural homogeneity and atomically flat basal planes—enabling, for the first time, the direct correlation between cleavage terminations and surface electronic topology. STM and DFT analyses reveal pronounced termination-dependent variations in Fermi surface morphology, indicating orbital-selective symmetry breaking and doping asymmetry at the atomic scale. These insights, together with the demonstrated capability to obtain large-area, well-ordered $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ flakes exhibiting high electrical conductivity and gate-independent transport, validate single-crystal MAX phases as ideal platforms for probing intrinsic MXene physics. By establishing a direct link between bulk crystal quality and surface-dependent functionalities, this work bridges the gap between fundamental MAX phase physics and practical MXene integration, laying the groundwork for next-generation 2D carbides with designer electronic interfaces and device-level performance.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available free of charge on Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by ERC-CZ program (project LL2101) from the Ministry of Education Youth and Sports (MEYS) and used large infrastructure from the project Advanced Functional Nanorobots (reg. No. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/15_003/0000444 financed by the EFRR). We also gratefully acknowledge the Czech computer infrastructure Metacentrum provided by the e-INFRA CZ project (ID: 90254), supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic. M.V. further acknowledge the support from the Czech Science Foundation (GACR No. 23-08083M). F.M.O. acknowledges the support from the Czech Science Foundation (GA ČR No. 25-16769S). This work was supported by Ministry of Education Youth and Sports (MEYS), project Advanced Multiscale Materials for Key Enabling Technologies (AMULET) from Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, co-funded by EU (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004558).

Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the study are accessible via the Zenodo repository: [xxxxxx](#).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no financial/commercial conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

B.W. and Z.S. conceived the project and supervised the overall research. B.W. conducted the majority of the experimental work, developed the methodology, and wrote the manuscript. F.L. performed Raman spectroscopy and device fabrication. X.L. and B.L.M. carried out HRTEM characterisation. M.V. conducted EBSD measurements. R.Y. contributed to the theoretical discussion. J.L. performed XPS analysis. K.J.S. conducted Hall effect measurements. F.M.O. revised the manuscript and the discussion of methodology. L.Z.

performed XRD measurements. All authors discussed the results and commented on the manuscript.

REFERENCES

- (1) Li, X.; Huang, Z.; Shuck, C. E.; Liang, G.; Gogotsi, Y.; Zhi, C., MXene chemistry, electrochemistry and energy storage applications. *Nature Reviews Chemistry* **2022**, *6* (6), 389-404.
- (2) Wu, B.; Li, M.; Mazánek, V.; Liao, Z.; Ying, Y.; Oliveira, F. M.; Dekanovsky, L.; Jan, L.; Hou, G.; Antonatos, N., In Situ Vanadium-Deficient Engineering of V₂C MXene: A Pathway to Enhanced Zinc-Ion Batteries. *Small Methods* **2024**, *8* (9), 2301461.
- (3) Oliveira, F. M.; Azadmanjiri, J.; Wang, X.; Yu, M.; Sofer, Z., Structure design and processing strategies of MXene-based materials for electromagnetic interference shielding. *Small Methods* **2023**, *7* (7), 2300112.
- (4) Shuck, C. E.; Sarycheva, A.; Anayee, M.; Levitt, A.; Zhu, Y.; Uzun, S.; Balitskiy, V.; Zahorodna, V.; Gogotsi, O.; Gogotsi, Y., Scalable synthesis of Ti₃C₂T_x mxene. In *MXenes*, Jenny Stanford Publishing: 2023; pp 539-560.
- (5) Downes, M.; Shuck, C. E.; Lord, R. W.; Anayee, M.; Shekhirev, M.; Wang, R. J.; Hryhorchuk, T.; Dahlqvist, M.; Rosen, J.; Gogotsi, Y., M₅X₄: a family of MXenes. *ACS nano* **2023**, *17* (17), 17158-17168.
- (6) He, Z.; Yao, L.; Guo, W.; Sun, N.; Wang, F.; Wang, Y.; Wang, R.; Wang, F., Pseudocapacitance of Bimetallic Solid-Solution MXene for Supercapacitors with Enhanced Electrochemical Energy Storage. *Advanced Functional Materials* **2023**, *33* (52), 2305251.
- (7) Hongxiang, Z.; Zhenying, H.; Mingxing, A.; Yang, Z.; Zhili, Z.; Shibo, L., Tribophysical properties of polycrystalline bulk Ti₃AlC₂. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* **2005**, *88* (11), 3270-3274.
- (8) Yang, L.; Wang, Y.; Wang, X.; Shafique, S.; Zheng, F.; Huang, L.; Liu, X.; Zhang, J.; Zhu, Y.; Xiao, C., Identification the Role of Grain Boundaries in Polycrystalline Photovoltaics via Advanced Atomic Force Microscope. *Small* **2024**, *20* (5), 2304362.
- (9) Ghasali, E.; Derakhshandeh, M. R.; Orooji, Y.; Alizadeh, M.; Ebadzadeh, T., Effects of 211 and 413 ordering on the corrosion behavior of V-Al-C MAX phases prepared by spark plasma sintering. *Journal of the European Ceramic Society* **2021**, *41* (9), 4774-4787.
- (10) Zhang, Q.; Xiao, Y.; Li, M.; Huang, Q., Ti₃AlC₂ single crystal growth via controlling horizontal temperature gradient. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* **2025**, *108* (4), e20287.
- (11) Anayee, M.; Shekhirev, M.; Wang, R.; Gogotsi, Y., Effect of oxygen substitution and oxycarbide formation on oxidation of Ti₃AlC₂ MAX phase. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* **2024**, *107* (9), 6334-6341.
- (12) Ouisse, T.; Sarigiannidou, E.; Chaix-Pluchery, O.; Roussel, H.; Doisneau, B.; Chaussende, D., High temperature solution growth and characterization of Cr₂AlC single crystals. *Journal of crystal growth* **2013**, *384*, 88-95.
- (13) Shi, L.; Ouisse, T.; Sarigiannidou, E.; Chaix-Pluchery, O.; Roussel, H.; Chaussende, D.; Hackens, B., Synthesis of single crystals of V₂AlC phase by high-temperature solution growth and slow cooling technique. *Acta Materialia* **2015**, *83*, 304-309.
- (14) Badr, H. O.; Champagne, A.; Ouisse, T.; Charlier, J.-C.; Barsoum, M. W., Elastic properties and hardness values of V₂AlC and Cr₂AlC single crystals. *Physical Review Materials* **2020**, *4* (8), 083605.
- (15) Ade, M.; Hillebrecht, H., Ternary borides Cr₂AlB₂, Cr₃AlB₄, and Cr₄AlB₆: The first members of the series (CrB₂)_nCrAl with n= 1, 2, 3 and a unifying concept for ternary borides as MAB-phases. *Inorganic chemistry* **2015**, *54* (13), 6122-6135.
- (16) Mortensen, J. J.; Hansen, L. B.; Jacobsen, K. W., Real-space grid implementation of the projector augmented wave method. *Physical Review B—Condensed Matter and Materials Physics* **2005**, *71* (3), 035109.
- (17) Enkovaara, J.; Rostgaard, C.; Mortensen, J. J.; Chen, J.; Dułak, M.; Ferrighi, L.; Gavnholt, J.; Glinsvad, C.; Haikola, V.; Hansen, H. A., Electronic structure calculations with GPAW: a real-space implementation of

- the projector-augmented-wave method. *Journal of physics: Condensed matter* **2010**, 22 (25), 253202.
- (18) Perdew, J. P.; Burke, K.; Ernzerhof, M., Generalized gradient approximation made simple. *Physical review letters* **1996**, 77 (18), 3865.
- (19) Grimme, S.; Antony, J.; Ehrlich, S.; Krieg, H., A consistent and accurate ab initio parametrization of density functional dispersion correction (DFT-D) for the 94 elements H-Pu. *The Journal of chemical physics* **2010**, 132 (15).
- (20) Presser, V.; Naguib, M.; Chaput, L.; Togo, A.; Hug, G.; Barsoum, M. W., First-order Raman scattering of the MAX phases: Ti₂AlN, Ti₂AlC_{0.5}N_{0.5}, Ti₂AlC_{(Ti_{0.5}V_{0.5})₂AlC}, V₂AlC, Ti₃AlC₂, and Ti₃GeC₂. *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy* **2012**, 43 (1), 168-172.
- (21) Shi, Y.; Wang, L.; Qiao, X.; Li, S.; Liu, Y.; Li, X.; Zhao, X., The Polarization Properties of the Reflection Spectra of Single-Layer MoS₂ and ReS₂ on SiO₂/Si and Quartz Substrates. *Nanoscale Research Letters* **2020**, 15, 1-6.
- (22) Natu, V.; Benchakar, M.; Canaff, C.; Habrioux, A.; Celerier, S.; Barsoum, M. W., A critical analysis of the X-ray photoelectron spectra of Ti₃C₂T_z MXenes. *Matter* **2021**, 4 (4), 1224-1251.
- (23) Näslund, L.-Å.; Persson, P. O.; Rosen, J., X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy of Ti₃AlC₂, Ti₃C₂T_z, and TiC provides evidence for the electrostatic interaction between laminated layers in MAX-phase materials. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2020**, 124 (50), 27732-27742.
- (24) Sondheimer, E. H.; Wilson, A. H., The theory of the magneto-resistance effects in metals. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences* **1947**, 190 (1023), 435-455.
- (25) Gonzalez-Julian, J., Processing of MAX phases: From synthesis to applications. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* **2021**, 104 (2), 659-690.
- (26) Tang, M.; Li, J.; Wang, Y.; Han, W.; Xu, S.; Lu, M.; Zhang, W.; Li, H., Surface terminations of MXene: synthesis, characterization, and properties. *Symmetry* **2022**, 14 (11), 2232.
- (27) Sarycheva, A.; Gogotsi, Y., Raman spectroscopy analysis of the structure and surface chemistry of Ti₃C₂T_x MXene. In *MXenes*, Jenny Stanford Publishing: 2023; pp 333-355.
- (28) Xu, C.; Wang, L.; Liu, Z.; Chen, L.; Guo, J.; Kang, N.; Ma, X.-L.; Cheng, H.-M.; Ren, W., Large-area high-quality 2D ultrathin Mo₂C superconducting crystals. *Nature materials* **2015**, 14 (11), 1135-1141.
- (29) Geng, D.; Zhao, X.; Chen, Z.; Sun, W.; Fu, W.; Chen, J.; Liu, W.; Zhou, W.; Loh, K. P., Direct synthesis of large-area 2D Mo₂C on in situ grown graphene. *Advanced Materials* **2017**, 29 (35), 1700072.
- (30) Wang, D.; Zhou, C.; Filatov, A. S.; Cho, W.; Lagunas, F.; Wang, M.; Vaikuntanathan, S.; Liu, C.; Klie, R. F.; Talapin, D. V., Direct synthesis and chemical vapor deposition of 2D carbide and nitride MXenes. *Science* **2023**, 379 (6638), 1242-1247.
- (31) Xu, X.; Guo, T.; Lanza, M.; Alshareef, H. N., Status and prospects of MXene-based nanoelectronic devices. *Matter* **2023**, 6 (3), 800-837.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Large-area Ti_3AlC_2 single crystals synthesised via TiAl_3 -assisted flux enable the preparation of millimetre-scale $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes with well-ordered structure and metallic transport characteristics.

